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Impact Factor: 3.43

IMPACT OF MICRO CREDIT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MICRO ENTERPRISES- A STUDY ON KOTTAYAM DISTRICT, KERALA

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ABSTRACT

Micro credit has been considering as a powerful tool for eradicating the poverty and improves the standard of living of people especially for those who are excluded from formal financial sector. Micro credit is a very small amount of loan proving to a group of people in order to conduct the Income Generating Activities (IGA) which leads to the profit and increase in savings of the members and ultimately the betterment of standard of living. In Kerala, a community-based, poverty reduction project of the Government, called Kudumbashree, is the major player who initiates to form SHG's from rural area and to provide assistance for them to setup micro enterprises, by providing micro loans. Besides Kudumbashree, several NGO's are also providing credible services to the rural society in order to institute and foster the performance of micro enterprises. The present study is an attempt to analyze the role of micro credit in the development of micro enterprises, in Kottayam district. This study conducted with the broad objective to determine availability of micro credit in micro enterprises, level of assistance provided by various micro finance institutions and the cost, sales, profit pattern of micro enterprises in order to understand the savings of members.

Keywords

Micro credit, Micro enterprises, SHG's, Kudumbashree, NGO's, Kottayam District.

Introduction

Micro credit is a part of micro finance refers to small amount of loan given to impoverished borrowers who typically lack collateral, steady employment and a verifiable credit history. One of the main objective of micro credit is to provide access to money to those who were normally excluded from formal financial sector, to set up their own income generating activities (IGA's). The history of micro credit linked to Nobel laureate Muhammad Yunus who is the founder of Grameen Bank, Bangladesh in 1983, considering as the first modern microcredit institution, providing financial support to rural poor. In India several institutions like NABARD, DICGE, SIDBI, and various RRB's providing financial support to that Micro Finance Institutions (MFI) who were directly providing microloans to the needy people.

Review of Literature

Several studies had been conducted in the area of micro credit program. A brief review of few significant works is done in this section.

Mohammed Shofi Ullah Mazumder and Lu Wencong (2013), states that micro-credit program helps to improve socio-economic status of the rural women. The involvement in credit program had a positive impact on different dimensions of the participants standard of living. There is a positive relationship between poverty reduction and access to micro-credit.

Study conducted by Reshmi R(2012) in order to understand the role of Kudumbashree especially in the area of micro enterprises with special reference to their marketing activities, finds that poor women's have truly empowered by joining Kudumbashree organ like NHG's and SHG's. Majority of the micro enterprises run by group member's in the study area showing a symptoms of profitability.

Jeet Singh and Preeti Yadav (2012), micro finance established as a powerful and potential tool for promoting governmental aim such as financial inclusion. Financial services are available to poor without having any collateral and it help them to avail assets and resources to do business.

Austin Joseph (2011) in his study concludes that , micro credit programmes helped the members to learn and practice management principles effectively and it leads to increase their efficiency in the areas of marketing, selling, organizing, planning and controlling various activities.

A study conducted by Dr.K .Rajendran , and Dr R.P Raya (2011), states that, Non-Governmental Organizations playing a vital role in helping rural women to form self-help groups and they motivated women to join self-help groups.

Dharen Kumar Pandey, Mukesh Kumar (2011), micro finance is considering as the only way to achieve financial inclusion to the rural poor. Through NGO's, MFI's and other agencies, SHG are always connected with NABARD, SIDBI, and other Commercial banks and make them available all financial resources they required.

M. Jahangir Alam Chowdhury (2008) Poverty of households decreases with the increase in microcredit program membership duration and microcredit loan size.

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the structural characteristics of micro enterprises in Kottayam district
2. To determine the accessibility of micro credit in micro enterprises.
3. To examine the level of support received from MFI's and the effect of it to the enterprise development
4. To analyze the cost, profitability, savings and repayment ability of micro enterprises units.

Research Methodology

The present study is both descriptive and empirical in nature. Both primary and secondary data have been used for the analyses. Primary data collected from the micro enterprises units working in the Kottayam district of Kerala. Secondary data have been collected from different books, journals, magazines, dissertations, periodicals, annual reports and publications of different agencies, websites etc related with the subject.

Tools for collecting Primary data

A well structured interview schedule was prepared for the collection of primary data from the micro enterprise units. A pilot study was conducted by collecting data from ten samples micro enterprises. After the pilot study the interview schedule was restructured and finalized.

Sample Design

Micro enterprise units working in the rural areas of Kottayam district having loans taken from different Micro Finance Institutions constitutes the universe. Firstly, the universe is classified into rural and urban areas. Secondly, they have been classified on the basis of concentration of micro enterprise units. That is six areas have been identified such as Aymanam, Cherppunkal, Chingavanam, Kaippuzha, Manarcad and Punnathura. Finally ten sample units have been selected from each selected concentrated areas. As a whole, sixty sample units constitute the sample size for the study.

Nature of Micro Enterprises Units

Table 1 depicts the classification of sample unit showing the nature of the sample unit's i.e. Micro –financial institutions and the type of business activities. It is clear that out of 60 samples are taken for the study, 24 samples are from Kottayam Service Society, 18 are from SNDP Union, 12 are from Shalom micro credit and remaining 6 are from Kudumbashree. Most of the SHG's are doing agricultural activities and animal husbandry under KSS. Retailing activities under SNDP union, Shalom micro credit .Under Kudumbashree, tailoring, food production and retailing units have placed equally. It is clear that most of the units are doing retailing business as compared to other type business of activities.

Table 1-MFI based classification of sample unit showing type of business activities engaged

MFI's \ ACTIVITIES	K.S.S	SNDP	Shalom	Kudumbashree	TOTAL	%
Tailoring and textiles	2	5	2	2	11	18.34
Retailing	5	8	3	2	18	30
Food production	5	1	1	2	9	15
Manufacture units	5	2	4	-	11	18.33
Agriculture& animal husbandry	7	2	2	-	11	18.33
Total	24	18	12	6	60	100

Source: Primary data

Number of Loan Cycle Completed

Table 2 depicts the MFI based classification of sample unit indicating number of loan cycle completed .Out of 24 units financed by Kottayam Service Society 17 units completed 1-6 loan cycles. 18 units financed by SNDP Union 16 units completed 1-6 loan cycle.12 units financed by Shalom micro credit, 11 units completed 1-6 loan cycle and all of them are completed 1-6 loan cycle out of 6 sample units under Kudumbashree.

Table 2-MFI based Classification of Sample Unit Showing Number of Loan Cycle Completed

NUMBER OF CYCLE COMPLETED MFI's	1-3 loan cycle	4-6 loan cycle	7-9 loan cycle	TOTAL	Percentage
	No of Samples	No of Samples	No of Samples		
Kottayam Service Society	8	9	7	24	40
SNDP Union	10	6	2	18	30
Shalom Micro Credit	7	4	1	12	20
Kudumbashree	5	1	-	6	10
Total	30	20	10	60	100

Source: Primary data

Analysis of Relationship between Loan and Profit

The relationship between average amount of loan taken and profit earned by the sampling units are presented in Table 3.

Table 3- Amount of Loan and Profit

Activities	Avg. amount of loan	Avg. amount of Profit	Total
Tailoring/ textile	84546	15973	100519
Retailing	99722	16117	115839
Food production	71111	12244	83355
Manufacturing unit	85000	12182	97182
Agriculture/animal husbandry	92727	15781	108508
Total	433106	72297	505403

Source: Primary data

Table 4 - ANOVA

Source of variation	Sum of squares	D.F	Mean square	F
Between Columns	1301766	1	1301766	Fc =304.29*
Between Rows	30158	4	7540	FR = 1.76
Residual	17112	4	4278	
Total	1349036	9		

Source: Primary data

* Significance at 5 % level

Ho: there is no significant relationship between average amount of loan taken and profit earned by the sampling units.

Result; calculated F value between columns (304.29) is higher than the table value (244.6) calculated at 5 % level of significance. So null hypothesis put forward by the researcher is rejected and establish that there is a significant relationship between average amount of loan taken and profit earned by the sampling units.

Average Amount of Sales, Cost, Profit and Percentage of Sales

Revenue and cost are the two main factors which determine the profit. It is the difference between sales and cost. Therefore it is important to analyze the total sales, cost and profit of the unit in order to find their financial efficiency.

Average amount of profit is higher among the retailing unit with an average amount of Rs16117 with a standard deviation of Rs8196. Average amount of profit for tailoring/textile unit is Rs15973 with a standard deviation of Rs12328. Average amount of profit of agriculture/animal husbandry unit is Rs15781 with a standard deviation of Rs7294. Food production units have an average amount of profit of Rs12244 and standard deviation of Rs8815. Average amount of profit of manufacturing unit is Rs12182 and the standard deviation is Rs4750. the consistency in the average amount of profit can be observed among the manufacturing unit(CV 38.99).

Table 5- Activity based Classification of Samples unit Showing the Average Amount Sales, Cost, Profit and Percentage of Profit on Sales.

Activities	Sales		Cost		Profit		Percentage of profit on sales
	Avg (Rs)	SD (Rs)	Avg (Rs)	SD (Rs)	Avg (Rs)	SD (Rs)	
Tailoring/textile	57791	36445 (63.06)	41818	32108 (76.78)	15973	12328 (77.18)	27.64%
Retailing	72289	34038 (47.09)	56172	28599 (50.91)	16117	8196 (50.85)	22.30%
Food production	48244	30439 (63.09)	36000	27815 (77.26)	12244	8815 (71.99)	25.36%
manufacturing Unit	48600	21494 (44.23)	36418	22113 (60.72)	12182	4750 (38.99)	25.07%
Agriculture/animal husbandry	70236	27823 (39.61)	54455	27642 (50.76)	15781	7294 (46.22)	22.47%

Source: Primary data

Figures in parenthesis denotes coefficient of variation

Relationship between Loan and Sales

The relationship between loan taken by the unit and the turnover of the sample unit; when other factors remain constant is depicted in the table 6.

Table 6- Relation between loan and sales

Sl.No	Activities	Correlation Co-efficient
1	Tailoring/textile Unit	0.87*
2	Retailing Unit	0.42*
3	Food production Unit	0.79*
4	Manufacturing Unit	0.20*
5	Agriculture/animal husbandry Unit	0.45*

Source: Primary data

*Significant at 5% level

H_0 : there is no significant relationship between loan taken by the units and turnover of the units. The correlation analysis shows that there is significant relationship between loan taken by the units and sales of the textile and food production units; and moderate relationship can be observed among the retailing and agriculture/animal husbandry units. Therefore, the null hypothesis can be rejected and H_1 can be established that there is a significant relationship between loan taken by the units and turnover of the units.

Average Amount of Profit, Repayment of Loan, Personal Expenses and Percentage of Profit on Sales

Micro credit enables the units for achieving profit and increasing the saving habit through which the living standards of the people can be improved. Table 7 demonstrates the classification of sample unit showing the average amount of profit, repayment, personal expenses, savings and the percentage of savings on profit.

Average amount of savings is highest for the tailoring/textile unit with an average amount of Rs6264 and a standard deviation of Rs6423. Average amount of savings of agriculture/animal husbandry is Rs5627 with a standard deviation of Rs4480. Average amount of savings of retailing unit is Rs5111 with a standard deviation of Rs4243. Food production units have an average amount of savings of Rs4700 and standard deviation of Rs4306.

Average amount of savings for manufacturing unit is Rs2773 and the standard deviation is Rs2071.the consistency in the average amount of savings can be observed among the manufacturing unit (CV=24.68)

Table 7- Activity based classification of sample unit showing the average amount profit, repayment of Loan, Personal Expenses, Savings and Percentage of Savings on Profit.

Activities	Profit		Repayment of Loan		Personal Expenses		Savings		% of savings on profit
	Avg (Rs)	SD (Rs)	Avg (Rs)	SD (Rs)	Avg (Rs)	SD (Rs)	Avg (Rs)	SD (Rs)	
Tailoring/textile	15973	12328 (77.18)	8727	6763 (77.50)	982	1565 (159.7)	6264	6423 (99.37)	39.22%
Retailing	16117	8196 (50.85)	10314	5301 (51.40)	692	1383 (199.8)	5111	4243 (83.02)	31.72%
Food production	12244	8815 (71.99)	7450	4677 (62.78)	94	24 (25.53)	4700	4306 (91.62)	38.39%
Manufacturing Unit	12182	4750 (38.99)	9018	4318 (47.88)	391	216 (55.24)	2773	2071 (24.68)	22.76%
Agriculture/animal husbandry	15781	7294 (46.22)	9686	4159 (42.94)	468	425 (90.81)	5627	4480 (79.62)	36.66%

Source: Primary data

SD=Standard Deviation

Figures in parenthesis denotes coefficient of variation

Relationship between Profit and Savings

The relationship between profit and savings of the sampling units are presented in Table 8.

Table 8- Average amount of profit and savings

Activities	Avg. amount of Profit	Avg. amount of Savings	Total
Tailoring/ textile	15973	6264	22237
Retailing	16117	5111	21228
Food production	12244	4700	16944
Manufacturing unit	12182	2773	14955
Agriculture/animal husbandry	15781	5627	21408
Total	72297	24475	96772

(Source: primary data)

Table 9- ANOVA

Source of variation	Sum of Squares	D.F	Mean square
Between samples	228694369	1	228694369
Within samples	23877347	8	2984668
Total	252571716	9	

(Source: primary data)

H₁: There is a significant relationship between profit earned and savings of the sampling units.

Result: F value (76.62) is less than the table value (238.9) calculated at 5 % level of significance for (1, 8) degree of freedom. So, the alternative hypothesis put forward by the researcher can be rejected and, **H₀:** There is no significant relationship between the profit earned and savings of the sampling units can be accepted.

Relationship between Loan and Savings

Table 10- relationship between loan and savings

SI.NO	Activities	Correlation Co-efficient
1	Tailoring/textile Unit	0.71*
2	Retailing Unit	0.23*
3	Food production Unit	0.93*
4	Manufacturing Unit	-0.12*
5	Agriculture/animal husbandry Unit	0.39*

Source: Primary data

*Significant at 5% level

The table 10 reveals that there is a high positive correlation between loan and savings of the textile unit; this indicates that an increase in the amount of loan will also increase the amount of savings of the units. There is a low positive correlation between loan and savings of retail unit. There exist a high positive correlation between loan and savings of food production unit. There is a negative correlation between loan and savings of the manufacturing unit. It is observed that moderate positive correlation between loan amount and the amount of savings of the agricultural/ animal husbandry units. Alternative hypothesis put forward by the researcher **H₁**; there is a significant relationship between loan taken by the units and savings of the units can be accepted.

Findings of the Study

- Most of the units under study are experienced, and engaged in income generating activities
- Most of the units are having loan ranging up to rupees one lakh. This indicated that their financial performance is good because loans are granted on the basis of the financial performance of the units
- Sales and profits of the units are highly depend upon the amount of credit availed to them
- Micro credit availability also helped the micro enterprises to increase the savings of them.
- Micro credits available to the units are helpful to them to improve the living standards.

Suggestions

- Reduce the interest rate or it should scrap off completely. If the rate is reduced, it will help them to increase their savings.
- More credit schemes should be made available.

Limitations

- Sample size has been collected only from the six prominent areas of Kottayam District. So it does not represent all the geographical coverage of the Kottayam District.
- All the sampling units are not willing to provide all the information's relating to the study such as, income, savings, personal expenses etc.
- From among the selected sample units, few of them are not keeping sufficient records and accounts of their activities.
- Time and cost was a limiting factor.

Conclusion

Based on the interviews and discussions with various SHG members who were running microenterprises, it has been observed that, the availability of micro credit in the form of microloans helps to improve the working efficiency of the micro enterprises. Their performance efficiency leads to increased sales and it leads to better profit. But at the same time interest charged by the MFI's for providing loan are almost equal or higher than the interest charged by other financial institutions. Increased cost of production stands as an obstacle for their revenue. Lack of timely and sufficient availability of loan, price fluctuations in the market, risk, competitions etc are some other problems faced by the micro enterprise units.

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Interview Schedule

Please provide the following information;

1. Type of economic engaged.....
2. Name of MFI
3. When did you receive the first loan from the Bank/MFI?
4. How many loan cycles have you completed?
5. How have you spent the past loans? How much?

Cycle 1-3:

Cycle 4-6:

Cycle 7-9:

6. Rate of interest of loan
7. Repayment structure of loan (Average amount for past 5 years)

Year	Repayment of loan

8. Average amount of sales, cost, expenses, profit and savings details.

Year	Sales	Cost of production	Personal expenses	Profit	Savings